

Potential pitfalls in the making on the way to 2030?

Intersecting the Scottish and Australian experiences on fair access to HE

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Dr Laurence Lasselle (University of St Andrews Business School, Department of Management, UK & 2024-25 ACSES Visiting Scholar, Australia)

Contact: laurence.lasselle@st-andrews.ac.uk

ACSES staff

ACSES is a national centre funded by the Australian government to undertake and fund research, policy, and trials work in Australia. The Centre was commissioned by the [Accord Review](#) to outline policy options in relation to parity targets for four equity groups in Australian HE, including people from low socio-economic status (low SES) backgrounds (low SES students) and people from rural and isolated (remote) areas (regional/remote students) ([ACSES, 2023](#)).

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Summary

- In Scotland, the sector has made a concerted and successful effort to widen access for the two national priority groups (NPGs), i.e. SIMD20 entrants (those residing in the 20% most deprived areas) and care-experienced (CE) entrants.
 - This effort was guided by the Fair Access to Higher Education (HE) policy, implemented since 2016.
 - This effort is documented by the sector's willingness to meet the interim targets (see [32](#)) and the publication of minimum entry requirements (MERs) for all undergraduate courses for NPGs (see [11](#)).
 - The 2030 equal access policy goal (see [32](#)) remains achievable (see [155](#)).
- However, two potential pitfalls raising concerns about access and equity are in the making.
- **First potential pitfall:** While the increase in SIMD20 entrants has significantly contributed to the overall rise in full-time first degree entrants at university from 2013-14 to 2023-24, a greater share of this expansion is an increase in the number of non-NPG entrants.
- **Second potential pitfall:** Some non-NPG socio-economically disadvantaged (SED) learners now experience greater competition from NPG learners and non-SED learners in accessing HE courses with demanding ERs.
 - While NPGs have benefited from the policy overall, some non-NPG SED learners are more at risk being left behind (among them are learners registered for free school meal and living in SIMD21-40 remote rural areas). Learners attending schools that mainly serve remote communities are less likely to meet the demanding ERs for some HE courses than those in schools serving non-remote communities post-COVID.
- Both potential pitfalls are still in the making and should be urgently addressed by the sector.
- This brief explains why and how the sector should further strengthen its efforts to achieve equal access by 2030 (and promote it beyond) by targeting more accurately socio-economic disadvantage. To do so, the sector should draw on its experience and use more judiciously the MERs by, e.g.:
 - Guaranteeing that all SED learners are eligible to apply under MERs.
 - Evaluating whether these MERs align with the minimum academic standard and subject knowledge required for the successful completion of HE courses with ERs, particularly those with demanding ERs (see [11](#) and [18](#)).
- Both potential pitfalls are discussed in the light of the most recent Australian Equity Group experience.
 - Australia has pursued a formal policy of identifying student equity groups since the mid-1990s and established national policy settings in view of findings from major systemic reviews, the most recent of which was undertaken by the Australian Universities Accord ("Accord Review"), who published their [Final Report](#) in early 2024.
 - A lesson for Scotland from Australia is that the combination of measures of disadvantage, including area measures, coupled with resourcing for widening participation and student success, can contribute to significant increases in equity student enrolment and success.

Brief's objectives, key recommendations & plan of actions

This brief explains why and how the sector should further strengthen its efforts to achieve equal access by 2030 for two reasons:

- Despite a remarkable increase in the number of entrants from NPGs, a greater share of the expansion in full-time first degree entrants at university from 2013-14 to 2023-24 is due to an increase in the number of non-NPG entrants.
- Some non-NPG SED learners now experience greater competition from NPG learners and non-SED learners in accessing HE. For instance, the non-NPG SED learners residing in remote communities face two types of additional barriers to their progression to HE from secondary education:
 - Systemic barriers since the implementation of the Fair Access to HE policy because of where they live, i.e. they do not live in SIMD20 zones and
 - Educational hurdles in the post-COVID era because of the schools they attend. The relative likelihood of schools serving mainly remote communities to schools serving mainly non-remote communities achieving demanding ER thresholds dropped.

To address both reasons and in line with (11) and (18), the brief stresses the necessity to target more accurately socio-economic disadvantage. It makes two recommendations to the sector based on the sector's experience since the implementation of policy:

- **Recommendation 1:** Guaranteeing that all SED learners are eligible to apply under MERs.
- **Recommendation 2:** Evaluating whether these MERs align with the minimum academic standard and subject knowledge required for the successful completion of HE courses, particularly those with demanding ERs.

Plan of actions

The brief advises for a stronger collaboration across the sector to ensure that all SED learners' applications to courses with demanding ERs are scrutinised against MERs. This strengthened collaboration would involve:

- Developing all "SED groups" enrolment projections for 2035.
- Identifying the list of schools whose attainment performances:
 - Either have remained below the national attainment performances at 2A and 4A grades at Higher for learners with 5 or more passes since 2022,
 - Or have declined since 2022.
- Including these schools in SHEP (Schools for Higher Education Programme) with the ambition to:
 - Dedicate outreach work with these schools, particularly those serving remote communities,
 - Foster attainment performance at A grades at Higher.

Potential pitfall 1 or How meaningful is the concerted and successful effort towards the 2030 goal?

Scottish context

The Fair Access to HE policy has been implemented since 2016. Its goal is that students from the 20% most deprived backgrounds should represent 20% of full-time first degree entrants to HE by 2030 (see 32 and 155).

The policy defines two NPGs:

- Young CE learners and
- Young learners from “*the most deprived backgrounds*” (see 32), i.e. young learners residing in areas captured by the first quintile of the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD), the so-called SIMD20 areas (the 20% most deprived areas in Scotland).

First potential pitfall: While the increase in SIMD20 entrants has significantly contributed to the overall rise in full-time first degree entrants at university from 2013-14 to 2023-24, a greater share of this expansion is an increase in the number of non-NPG entrants.

Between 2013-14 and 2023-24, Table 1 reports the impressive growth rate of 51.8% for the two NPGs—which reflects the concerted and successful effort to widen access—but highlights that the growth of undergraduates is led by the growth of the undergraduates not belonging to NPGs (54.3%). In other words, the expansion of the university sector has been beneficial to all undergraduates, particularly those from non-NPGs. Meeting the 2030 goal (20%) from the 2023-24 share (16.7%) could be arduous, as evidenced by the outcome of a similar goal in Australia.

Table 1: Scottish-domiciled full-time first degree entrants at university, by 20% most deprived areas and care experience, 2013-14 and 2023-2024. Growth in %.

	2013-14	Share (%)	2023-24	Share (%)	2013-14 to 2023-24 Growth (%)	Share of Growth (%)
Undergraduates	28,285	100.0	32,810	100.0	16%	-
SIMD20 entrants	3,850	13.7%	5,445	16.7%	41.4%	35.2%
CE entrants	145	0.5%	620	1.9%	327.6%	10.5%
Two NPGs*	3,995	14.1%	6,065	18.5%	51.8%	45.7%
Non-NPGs*	24,290	85.9%	26,745	81.5%	10.1%	54.3%

Notes: Data (in black) from [ROWA 2023-24](#) (see also Table 3 below); additional information (in purple) provided by Laurence’s examination.

*There is double counting. Laurence is unable to distinguish the CE entrants residing in SIMD20 zones from those residing in non-SIMD20 zones. She estimates this double counting to be around 192 in 2023-24 (see Point 18 in [ROWA 2023-24](#); no similar information is available in [ROWA 2016-17](#)). The 2013-14 to 2023-24 growth rate of non-NPGs and their share of growth should increase once double-counting is corrected.

According to Table 1, the growth between 2013-14 and 2023-24 in Scotland represented a significant expansion in HE participation, with Scottish-domiciled full-time first degree entrants at university and all undergraduate HE rising by 16% from 28,285 in 2013-14 to 32,810 in 2023-24. NPGs saw

particularly major growth in numbers, with overall growth reaching 51.8% over this period and both groups seeing faster growth than that seen overall.

The CE entrants achieved remarkable growth (+327.6%), indicating a welcome increase in self-reporting. The SIMD20 entrants demonstrated strong gains (+41.4%), showing the success of the tracking system. Both growths reveal a rising awareness among Scottish HE institutions of their responsibilities to these NPGs. They reflect a concerted and successful effort to widen participation through a marked focus on outreach programs and the use of contextualised admissions.

The Australian experience

A key finding from the [ACSES report](#) (2023) is the persistent under-representation of equity group students in Australian HE. As an example, low socioeconomic status (SES) students in Australia are defined as those students whose permanent home addresses are located in areas containing the bottom 25% of the Australian population on the basis of education and occupation outcomes reported to the Australian Census. In 2008, only 16.3% of Australian domestic HE students were classified as low SES, compared with the 25% population benchmark, with this share rising marginally to 17.1% in 2021. Similar disparities can be seen among the other major equity groups (Regional/Remote, First Nations, and Disability) and have been observed over the past 30 years of national data collection. Indeed, their initial observation led to national reporting in the first instance ([Australian Universities Accord](#), 2024). However, as Table 2 shows, equity group shares saw some improvement between 2008 and 2021, as the consequence of a major expansion in HE enrolment and policy to widen access, with domestic undergraduate numbers rising by nearly half (47.3%) from 532,503 in 2008 to 784,219 in 2021. Notably, equity group enrolments saw particularly strong growth, with overall growth reaching 75.3% over this period and all four major groups seeing faster growth than that seen overall.

Table 2: Domestic undergraduate enrolments, Australia 2008 and 2021, Growth %.

	2008	Share (%)	2021	Share (%)	2008 to 2021 Growth (%)	Share of Growth (%)
Undergraduates	532,503	100.0	784,219	100.0	47.3	-
Low SES	86,561	16.3	133,901	17.1	54.7	18.8
Regional/Remote	106,579	20.0	160,542	20.5	50.6	21.4
First Nations	6,820	1.3	16,383	2.1	144.9	3.8
Disability	23,447	4.4	80,769	10.2	246.9	22.8
Equity Group*	176,492	33.1	309,360	39.4	75.3	52.8
<i>Non-Equity</i>	<i>356,011</i>	<i>66.9</i>	<i>474,859</i>	<i>60.6</i>	<i>33.4</i>	<i>47.2</i>

Note: *The *Equity Group* measure is a sum of the four groups under consideration, adjusting for membership of multiple equity groups.

Source: [ACSES \(2023\)](#)

Much of this growth was concentrated in the Disability group, indicating both a rising awareness among institutions of their responsibilities to, and support for, students with disability, as well as a welcome increase in self-reporting among students. The enrolment growth rates of low SES and regional and remote students, groups defined using student home location, saw more modest gains. However, this is in and of itself an achievement given the lift in student numbers from these areas.

This reflects a concerted effort to widen participation in Australia through a marked focus on outreach programs, particularly in low SES and regional and remote areas.

Recent data from Australia show that the enrolment shares of low SES and regional/ remote students, which were declining prior to COVID, saw a steeper decline during and after the pandemic year, albeit with evidence of stabilisation and the beginning of a partial recovery in 2023 ([Australian Universities Accord](#), 2024). This highlights a pattern in the post-COVID era, whereby equity issues were exacerbated, with effects tending to linger and presenting a challenge to the sector ([O’Shea et al.](#), 2021).

Lesson for Scotland

A lesson for Scotland from Australia is that the combination of suitable measures of disadvantage, including area measures, coupled with resourcing for widening participation and student success, can contribute to significant increases in equity student enrolment even in a system with relatively high levels of tertiary education participation.

Additional queries for Scotland

Australian data show that the use of multiple measures of disadvantages enlarge access and participation to more under-represented groups in HE. A similar approach should be developed in Scotland to target more accurately socio-economic disadvantage and foster access for NPGs and non-NPGs SED learners beyond 2030.

Australian data show that – although the number of under-represented students massively increased in the HE system – the 2020 goal to have 25% of students from low SES backgrounds was not achieved. Scottish data have already revealed an uneven trajectory towards the 2030 goal, see for instance the trend from 2021-22 to 2023-24 reported in Table 3. Developing all “SED groups” enrolment projections for 2035 should rejuvenate the sector’s concerted effort on equal access.

Table 3: COWA key indicators from 2013-14 to 2023-24

COWA Key Indicators	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2023-24
Total Entrants	28,285	28,640	28,770	28,885	29,880	31,065	30,620	33,290	33,885	32,760	32,810
Entrants from MD20	3,850	3,965	4,015	3,965	4,650	4,900	4,970	5,515	5,595	5,310	5,445
% MD20 entrants	13.70%	13.90%	14.00%	13.80%	15.60%	15.90%	16.40%	16.70%	16.50%	16.30%	16.70%
CE Entrants	145	170	160	170	255	320	370	510	545	585	620
% CE entrants	0.50%	0.60%	0.60%	0.60%	0.80%	1.00%	1.20%	1.50%	1.60%	1.80%	1.90%

Source: [ROWA 2023-24](#)

Potential pitfall 2 or What about the non-NPG SED learners?

Non-NPG SED learners in the Scottish context

The policy's narrow focus on SIMD20 and CE risks marginalising non-NPG SED learners beyond SIMD20 areas, notably in remote areas, where evidence indicates low progression rate from secondary education to HE.

State secondary schools statistics characterise two additional groups of SED learners beyond the NPG definition: those registered for free school meals (FSM) and those residing both in the second SIMD quintile and "Remote Small Towns" or "Remote Rural Areas" as per the six-fold urban-rural classification.¹ According to Figure 2, schools with proportions of SED learners higher than the national (dataset) average (the so-called "Schools with higher SED") have lower average progression rates to HE compared to those with lower proportions. For Remote schools, the post-COVID progression rates are even lower than the pre-COVID rates.

Figure 2: Pre- and post-COVID 3-year average progression rates to HE (in %)

Source: Laurence Lasselle (2026b)

Laurence's analysis of disaggregated state secondary schools statistics indicates that some SED learners currently excluded from the NPGs may face barriers to their progression from secondary education to HE courses with demanding ERs because of where they live, the schools they attend, or the ERs set by the Scottish HE institutions offering these courses.

¹Lasselle (2026a). This is a novel framework resting on the use of disaggregation techniques combining remoteness granularity and deprivation contextualisation inspired by [Lasselle and Johnson \(2021\)](#) and [Lasselle \(2021\)](#) and the thriving Australian Rural Education research. It deliberately adopts the remote communities' perspective.

Evidence of systemic barriers and educational hurdles for non-NPG SED learners residing in remote communities to their progression from secondary education to HE courses with demanding ERs

- Since the implementation of the Fair Access to HE policy, the non-NPG SED learners residing in remote communities face new *systemic barriers* to their progression to HE because of where they live (see [Appendix 4](#)). They do not live in SIMD20 areas.
- These learners face an *educational hurdle* to their progression to HE because of the schools they attend and the demanding standard entry requirements (SERs) for some courses offered by some Scottish HE institutions.
 - As they do not belong to the NPGs, they must meet these demanding SERs in terms of SQA Higher set by Scottish HE institutions. However, their schools' attainment performance in terms of the percentage of learners achieving at least these SERs declined post-COVID. As a result, these learners may be less likely to meet these requirements (see [Appendix 5](#)).
 - In addition, these learners' progression to HE may be dampened because of two intertwined reasons. First, the learners in non-remote communities largely outnumber them. Second, schools serving non-remote communities improved their attainment performance at this SER threshold post-COVID.
- If these learners could apply for the MERs for these courses, they would face an *educational hurdle*.
 - Indeed, their schools' attainment performance in terms of the percentage of learners achieving at least these demanding MERs declined post-COVID.
 - In addition, schools serving non-remote communities, particularly those with significant proportions of SED learners, improved their attainment performance at the MER threshold post-COVID (see [Appendix 6](#)).

Second potential pitfall: Some non-NPG SED learners now experience greater competition from NPG learners and non-SED learners in accessing HE courses with demanding ERs.

Notes: Demanding SERs are those stipulating a minimum of 4A grades at Higher for learners with 5 or more passes (the so-called "demanding SER threshold"). Demanding MERs are those stipulating a minimum of 2A grades at Higher for these learners (the so-called "demanding MER threshold").

These findings lead to the two following recommendations to target more accurately socio-economic disadvantage

- **Recommendation 1:** Guaranteeing that all SED learners are eligible to apply under MERs (see [Appendix 7](#))
- **Recommendation 2:** Evaluate whether these MERs align with the minimum academic standard and subject knowledge required for the successful completion of demanding courses in HE.

The need for this work is pressing. We are four years away to achieve the 2030 goal and Australia's experience points out critical implementation challenges.

The Australian equity experience

In practice, in terms of equity policy, the [Accord Review](#) (2024) focuses on the key under-represented groups in HE and proposes a revised plan of actions. It recommended that

- Under-represented groups should participate in Australian HE at rates aligned to their proportion of the Australian population by 2050 (i.e. parity targets).
- The Australian government recognises that the “*urgent action to establish the right trajectory must start today*” ([Australian Universities Accord](#), 2024, p. 3). This includes continued funding of access and outreach programs in Australia, specific funding to universities to implement measures to ensure student success, and a review of baseline funding to institutions to ensure it reflects the differential costs of educating equity group students – known as “needs-based funding” (NBF).
- The Australian government introduces a “Managed Growth Funding” system, whereby the total allocation of places for (non-medical) domestic undergraduate courses in Australia is shaped in relation to the projected demand for places amongst equity group students and institutional performance against equity enrolment indicators.
- The creation of the [Australian Tertiary Education Commission](#) (ATEC) to oversee policy implementation in Australian HE, including in relation to the establishment of targets for equity group enrolments, work on the NBF, and informing government on the Managed Growth System. The ATEC has since been established, with its core operations commencing in January 2026.

The fast-approaching 2030 goal, the need to promote equality of access post-2030, and lessons from Australia’s recent experience, which highlight both opportunities and risks for similar policies suggest the need for a stronger collaboration across the sector to target more accurately socio-economic disadvantage. The sector should ensure that more SED learners access to HE and all SED learners’ applications to HE courses with demanding ERs are scrutinised against MERs. A plan of actions can be to:

- Develop all “SED groups” enrolment projections for 2035 and beyond.
- Identify the list of schools whose attainment performances:
 - Either have remained below the national attainment performances at 2A and 4A grades at Higher for learners with 5 or more passes since 2022,
 - Or have declined since 2022.
- Include these schools in SHEP (Schools for Higher Education Programme) with the ambition to:
 - Dedicate outreach work with these schools, particularly those serving remote communities,
 - Foster attainment performance at A grades at Higher.

Conclusion

Since the implementation of the Fair Access to HE policy in 2016, and particularly in the post-Covid era, new barriers to progression to HE courses with demanding ERs have emerged. These barriers are closely linked to geographic location (specifically non-SIMD20 zones) and academic attainment at A grades at Higher. They are particularly faced by non-NPG SED learners in remote communities.

In response, the sector should aim to target accurately socio-economic disadvantage. To do so, it must urgently ponder

- Which categories of learners qualify to apply under MERs (see [Appendix 7](#)) and
- Whether the ambitious MERs are set at a level which correctly reflects the minimum academic standard and subject knowledge required for the successful completion of HE courses, particularly those with demanding ERs.

This reflective and collaborative process should enable the sector to have a better understanding of the direct and indirect “costs” associated with educating NPGs and other widening access learners eligible to apply under MERs (see [162](#) and [163](#)).

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Appendix 1

Extract from [COWA \(2016\) A blueprint for fairness](#)

Recommendation 11. By 2019 all universities should set access thresholds for all degree programmes against which learners from the most deprived backgrounds should be assessed. These access thresholds should be separate to standard entrance requirements and set as ambitiously as possible, at a level which accurately reflects the minimum academic standard and subject knowledge necessary to successfully complete a degree programme.

Recommendation 18. Universities, colleges and local authorities should work together to provide access to a range of Higher and Advanced Higher subjects, which ensures that those from disadvantaged backgrounds or living in rural areas are not restricted in their ability to access higher education by the subject choices available to them.

Recommendation 32. The Scottish Government and the Scottish Funding Council should implement the following targets to drive forward the delivery of equal access in Scotland:

To realise the First Minister's ambition of equality of access to higher education in Scotland:

- By 2030, students from the 20% most deprived backgrounds should represent 20% of entrants to higher education. Equality of access should be seen in both the college sector and the university sector.

To drive progress toward this goal:

- By 2021, students from the 20% most deprived backgrounds should represent at least 16% of full-time first degree entrants to Scottish universities as a whole.
- By 2021, students from the 20% most deprived backgrounds should represent at least 10% of full-time first degree entrants to every individual Scottish university.
- By 2026, students from the 20% most deprived backgrounds should represent at least 18% of full-time first degree entrants to Scottish universities as a whole.

Extract from [The Scottish Parliament Education, Children and Young People Committee \(2025\)](#)

[Widening access to HE inquiry](#)

22. Minimum Entry Requirements (MERs) are the minimum grades an institution believes is required for successful completion of a course. To qualify to apply under MERs, an applicant must be* from an SIMD20 area and/or be care experienced.

155. The Committee notes the evidence suggesting it is difficult to say whether the interim target, whereby students from the 20% most deprived backgrounds should represent at least 18% of full-time first-degree entrants to Scottish universities as a whole by 2026, will be met. The Committee also notes the evidence suggesting that the 2030 target for 20% of full-time, first-degree entrants to be from SIMD20 areas remains achievable.

162. Given the importance of ensuring that students not only gain access to university but that they thrive when there, the Committee agrees that retention should be a priority area in the context of widening access. The Committee recommends that the Scottish Government should collate and analyse retention data throughout a widening access student's time at university, rather than maintaining the current focus on the end of year one and on course completion. This will help provide a better picture of that student's experience, and potentially highlight any barriers that may arise throughout their time at university.

163. In addition, the Committee notes the evidence it heard, which suggests that if universities wish to improve retention amongst widening access learners, the focus should be on tackling financial barriers and improving mental health support. The Committee recommends that the Scottish Government factors this evidence into its own work on widening access and retention.

212. The Committee notes the usefulness of using SIMD as a widening access measure, however, it also notes its limitations - particularly in relation to rural areas - and recommends that the Scottish Government works with stakeholders and the Commissioner to introduce a basket of measures to identify person-centred characteristics for widening access measures.

213. The Committee notes that there was a general consensus among witnesses that free school meals (FSM) eligibility could be used in addition to SIMD as a means of identifying students eligible for widening access measures.

**Laurence does not think it should be “must be”. In practice, the admission policy of each university clarifies the learners who qualify to apply under MERs. However, the interim targets of the Fair Access to HE policy are restricted to the SIMD20 entrants in [Recommendation 32](#). The second sentence in [22](#) could be rewritten as: Applicants from SIMD20 areas and care-experienced applicants automatically qualify to apply under MERs.*

Appendix 2: Definitions and abbreviations

- CE: Care-experience
- ERs: Entry requirements; MER: Minimum entry requirements; SER: Standard entry requirements
- HE: Higher education
- SIMD: Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation; SIMD20 areas: the 20% most deprived areas in Scotland
- Young: Undergraduate students are considered young if they are under 21 and mature if they are 21 or over on the start of their Engagement ([HESA](#))
- A NonRemote School is a state secondary school whose proportion of learners residing in “Remote Rural Areas” and “Remote Small Towns” (as per the six-fold urban-rural classification) is below 20%. These schools predominantly serve communities in “Large Urban Areas”, “Other Urban Areas”, or “Accessible Small Towns”. Few serve predominantly “Accessible Rural Areas”.
- A Remote School is a state secondary school whose proportion of learners residing in “Remote Rural Areas” and “Remote Small Towns” (as per the six-fold urban-rural classification) is at least 50%.
- *Socio-economic disadvantage* (SED) is identified from the SIMD ranking of the learners’ residence, the learners’ free school meal (FSM) registration, or residence in “Remote Rural Areas” and “Remote Small Towns”.
- Attainment performance
 - The *national (dataset) attainment performance at the SQA Higher standard entry requirements (the so-called SER threshold)* is measured by the 3-year average percentage of learners gaining at least 4A at Higher in state secondary schools (HE courses with demanding SERs are often at 4A at Higher).
 - The *school attainment performance at the SER threshold* is measured by the 3-year average percentage of its learners gaining at least 4A at Higher.
 - The *national (dataset) attainment performance at the SQA Higher minimum entry requirements (the so-called MER threshold)* is measured by the 3-year average percentage of learners gaining at least 2A at Higher in state secondary schools (HE courses with demanding MERs are often at 2A at Higher).
 - The *school attainment performance at the MER threshold* is measured by the 3-year average percentage of its learners gaining at least 2A at Higher.
- Pre- and post-COVID era (Scottish dataset)
 - Pre-COVID: 2017, 2018 and 2019
 - Post-COVID: 2022, 2023 and 2024

Appendix 3: Data

Dataset: **340 state secondary schools**. In this brief, Laurence only considers the secondary schools open in **2019 and in 2024**. The 2019 dataset has 358 schools. The 2024 dataset has 360 schools. She excluded from both datasets any schools that:

- closed and/or merged between 2020 and 2024
- opened between 2020 and 2024
- are “Junior” secondary schools
- do not have SQA Higher data over the pre- and post-COVID eras
- do not have the same Remote/NonRemote criterion for both dates.

The dataset has

- 56 Remote Schools
- 279 NonRemote Schools
- Only five schools have a percentage between at least 20% and less than 50%. This is the reason this brief only focuses on Remote and NonRemote Schools. However, their statistics are included in the computation of the national (dataset) average of every variable.

Appendix 4: Documentation of the systemic barriers

- The systemic barriers are created by the sole use of the SIMD20 measure. They can be documented by comparing the proportion of SIMD20 learners in Remote and NonRemote Schools. NonRemote Schools had more sizeable proportions of SIMD20 learners in both 2019 and 2024. In other words, there is a low likelihood that Remote Schools have significant proportions of their learners residing in SIMD20 areas. Indeed, Laurence’s research highlights that:
 - In 2019, a NonRemote School was 6.6 times more likely than a Remote School to have at least the national (dataset) average of 20.5% of its learners residing in the areas belonging to the first SIMD quintile.
 - In 2024, a NonRemote School was 4.3 times more likely than a Remote School to have at least the national (dataset) average of 21.2% of its learners residing in the areas belonging to the first SIMD quintile.

Appendix 5: Documentation of the educational hurdle to the progression to HE courses with demanding SERs (at least 4A grades at Higher)

- According to Table 4
 - The number of Remote Schools achieving the national (dataset) attainment performance at this demanding SER threshold dropped.
 - The Remote Schools’ attainment performances remained below the national (dataset) attainment performances at this SER threshold.
 - The Remote Schools did not improve their attainment performance at this SER threshold as much as the NonRemote Schools pre- and post-COVID eras.
 - The relative likelihood of Remote Schools versus NonRemote Schools achieving the national (dataset) attainment performance at this SER threshold declined. The ratio is now in favour of the NonRemote Schools.

Table 4: Demanding SER threshold and pre- and post-COVID schools’ attainment performance

	2019	2024
Demanding SER threshold	5.6% ^a	7.4% ^b
Attainment performance at this SER threshold		
Remote Schools	5.2% ⁺	6.2%
NonRemote Schools	5.7%	7.6%
Number of Remote Schools achieving this SER threshold	25	22
Ratio of Remote Schools to NonRemote Schools achieving this SER threshold	1.2 [*]	0.9

Source: Lasselie (2026b)

Notes:

^aThe 3-year average percentage of learners achieving the demanding SER threshold was 5.6% (average of the years 2017, 2018 and 2019).

^bThe 3-year average percentage of learners achieving this SER threshold was 7.4% (average of the years 2022, 2023 and 2024).

⁺5.2% of learners attending Remote Schools achieved this SER threshold over the years 2017, 2018 and 2019. In other words, the 3-year average percentage (2017-18-19) of learners gaining at least 4A at Higher for Remote Schools is 5.2%.

^{*}In 2019, a Remote School was 1.2 times more likely than a NonRemote School to have at least an average of 5.6% (the 2017-18-19 national (dataset) average) of its learners gaining at least 4A at Higher.

- In other words, as
 - the learners in NonRemote Schools largely outnumber the learners in Remote Schools, AND
 - the learners in NonRemote Schools are more likely to attend a school whose attainment performance at this demanding SER threshold improved between 2019 and 2024, AND
 - the SIMD20 learners are more likely to attend NonRemote Schools than Remote Schools, AND
 - the number of Remote Schools achieving the national (dataset) attainment performance at this SER threshold declined between 2019 and 2024, AND
 - the Remote Schools did not improve their attainment performance at this SER threshold as much as the NonRemote Schools did between 2019 and 2024, AND
 - the Remote Schools’ attainment performances remained below the national (dataset) attainment performances at the SER threshold,
 non-NPG SED learners in “Remote Rural Areas or “Remote Small Towns” are more and more unlikely to meet demanding SERs.

Appendix 6: Documentation of the educational hurdle to the progression to HE courses with demanding MERs (at least 2A grades at Higher)

- According to Table 5
 - The number of Remote Schools achieving the national (dataset) attainment performance at this demanding MER threshold dropped.
 - The Remote Schools’ attainment performances remained below the national (dataset) attainment performance at this MER threshold.
 - The Remote Schools did not improve their attainment performance at this MER threshold as much as the NonRemote Schools pre- and post-COVID eras.
 - The relative likelihood of Remote Schools versus NonRemote Schools achieving the national (dataset) attainment performance at this MER threshold declined. The ratio is now in favour of the NonRemote Schools.

Table 5: Demanding MER threshold and pre- and post-COVID schools’ attainment performance

	2019	2024
Demanding MER threshold	17.5% ^a	20.7% ^b
Attainment performance at this MER threshold		
Remote Schools	16.5% ⁺	18.5%
NonRemote Schools	17.7% ⁺	21.2%
Number of Remote Schools achieving this MER threshold	26	22
Ratio of Remote Schools to NonRemote Schools achieving this MER threshold	1.0 [*]	0.8

Source: Lasselle (2026b)

Notes:

^aThe 3-year average percentage of learners achieving the demanding MER threshold was 17.5% (average of the years 2017, 2018 and 2019).

^bThe 3-year average percentage of learners achieving this MER threshold was 20.7% (average of the years 2022, 2023 and 2024).

⁺16.5% of learners attending Remote Schools achieved this MER threshold over the years 2017, 2018 and 2019. In other words, the 3-year average percentage (2017-18-19) of learners gaining at least 2A at Higher for Remote Schools is 16.5%.

^{*}In 2019, a Remote School was as likely as a NonRemote School to have at least an average of 17.5% (the 2017-18-19 national (dataset) average) of its learners gaining at least 2A at Higher.

- In other words, as
 - the learners in NonRemote Schools largely outnumber the learners in Remote Schools, AND
 - the learners in NonRemote Schools are more likely to attend a school whose attainment performance at this demanding MER threshold improved between 2019 and 2024, AND
 - the number of Remote Schools achieving the national attainment performance at this MER threshold declined between 2019 and 2024, AND

- the Remote Schools did not improve their attainment performance at this MER threshold as much as the NonRemote Schools did between 2019 and 2024, AND
 - the Remote Schools’ attainment performances remained below the national (dataset) attainment performances at this MER threshold,
- non-NPG SED learners in in “Remote Rural Areas or “Remote Small Towns” are more and more unlikely to meet demanding MERs.

Appendix 7: Examples of SED learners who can or cannot apply under MERs (see Table 6).

Table 6: MERs and SERs for HE courses and SED learners

Category of learners	Apply under MERs? (11) & (22)
SIMD20 learners	They qualify to apply under MERs.
CE learners	They qualify to apply under MERs.
Non-CE & non-SIMD20 learners registered for FSM	They qualify to apply under SERs. <i>They could be asked to meet MERs depending on the university.</i>
Non-CE & SIMD21-40 learners residing in remote areas	They qualify to apply under SERs. <i>They could be asked to meet MERs depending on the university.</i>

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Contact: laurence.lasselle@st-andrews.ac.uk

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